

The connection of the Uzbek language with foreign languages

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Abstract:In this article,the relevance of Uzbek language in the comprehensive developmentand highlights its close connection with foreign languages of great international valueare described

Key words:the communication of languages , Uzbek language history,modern language,foreign language certificate,activity,cooperation.

Introduction:Uzbek language has seen significant development in terms of its historical,political,economic ,and cultural significance.Since its creation,our national language has passed through many stagesup to the present day,gaining value among the language of the world.The field of ancient Turkish language studies as a subject was introduced in Uzbekistan in 1980s.In other Turkish-speaking republics,it began in 1960s.During the period,the ancient Turkish language became one of the mainobjects of Turkology,attracting the attention of Turkologists since the 19th century.By the 20th century,after Uzbek was given the status of the state language increased significantly.Laws and regulations were created in this regard.Annual year,the 21st of October is established as thenational language day in our country,and various events and celebrations are held.Of course, theimportance of its connection with foreign languages in the development of our national languageis undeniable.Main body The connection of Uzbek language with foreign languages is very broad.This connection is basedon historical,political,cultural,and economic reasons.The relationship of Uzbek language with Turkish languages ,such as,Kazakh,Turkmen,Kyrgyz,and Turkic languages is based on historical and enthic reasons.Many Turkic words are used in the Uzbek language and, therefore,its connection with Turkish language is considered strong.

Political reasons,Uzbekistan's geographical location leads to a broader connection withn foreign languages.Uzbekistan maintains diplomatic,econpomic ,and cultural relations with countries across the world.This creates opportunities to learn,educate ,and use foreign languages.From an economic perspective,Uzbekistan,as an integrated nation into the global economic system,is striving to enhance its connection with foreign languages.Knowledge of foreign languages,their use,and communication with them creates additional opportunities for economic

development. From a cultural perspective, Uzbekistan is developing its connection with foreign languages to showcase its national culture

Globally. For example, Uzbek artists, literate, and music experts are recognized worldwide, and they learn foreign languages to present their creations to the world. In addition to all of these, during the process of globalization, Uzbekistan's relations with the countries of the world are expanding, and this requires learning and using foreign languages.

Improving the quality of education, developing the teaching of foreign languages, and enhancing students' skills and competence in learning foreign languages has become one of the priority tasks of the state policy in the field of education. It is necessary for our children to learn not only the national language and foreign languages at school, but also to acquire skills such as working with computers.

It is responsibility of the teachers in higher education institutions to deeply study and teach foreign Languages, using the best innovative pedagogical practices from advanced countries, and based this, to create an effective modern methodology for teaching foreign languages. Developing modern communicative competency-based methodology for teaching foreign languages and creating innovative educational programs based on evaluating students' language skills are also important tasks for all levels of the education system. It is of the most importance to promote scientific activities that are geared towards new approaches to teaching foreign languages, with a primary focus on the practical efficiency of scientific work. It is undeniable that the direct implementation of the methods developed by researchers in educational institutions through practical testing systems can yield effective results.

In higher education institutions in our country, the creation of electronic software platforms that provide a unique set of materials for modern teaching-methodological and assessment of knowledge in the field of teaching foreign languages, tailored to the philological education and specialties, appears to be necessary. The main goal of all these issues is the creation of modern and innovative pedagogical technologies and educational methods in teaching foreign languages in our country. Allowing foreign languages students to think freely and creatively and providing deep education based on the abilities of each student in specific directions can yield good results.

In this regard, the creation of new textbooks, the establishment of effective learning standards and methodologies in the education system are required. During this

process, and all individuals involved in education to actively participate in the practical activities of the wider community.

Respected President, If our children learn foreign languages, vocational skills, and computer literacy from schools, it will lead to positive changes and high development in society. It is necessary to emphasize that it is vital for our children to master at least two foreign languages as this is crucial in today's world where these languages are widely used in the production of goods, services, and international communication. It is regrettable that previously, in our country, languages such as French, German, and Spanish were taught alongside English. Unfortunately, in recent years the focus on learning languages other than English has diminished. Past mistakes have led to a situation where these languages are almost completely neglected in schools. The quality of teaching foreign languages is closely related to the training of teachers who have acquired modern knowledge and possess a high level of proficiency in foreign language skills. Students and professors are encouraged to obtain international and national qualification certificates such as IELTS, CEFR, APTIS, TKT, CELTA, and TESOL to measure their proficiency in foreign languages. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to provide students with a high level of foreign language proficiency using modern teaching methods and technologies. Foreign languages are considered as the main specialization in the pedagogical direction for admission exams to the higher education institutions. Instead of the traditional test, it is necessary to admit students based on the "National Qualification in Foreign Language Proficiency" test according to four language skills. By preparing for the traditional test, applicants only learn the grammar of a foreign language, which ultimately does not develop their communicative competence, such as speaking, listening, writing, and reading skills, and does not meet the CEFR requirements.

Introducing conditions for working with Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in educational institutions provide beneficial preparation for students in the foreign languages program. For this, it is recommended to implement the principles of dual education in organizing the educational process for students completing the program. This means that additional qualifications in foreign languages are given to students graduating from specific fields, providing them with the opportunity to become specialists who can teach their field in English, for instance. It is incumbent upon every educator to keep in mind the idea of our President 'Najot-in education, najot-in knowledge. Because, all good objectives are achieved through education and upbringing.'

In conclusion, it can be said that by learning languages, we contribute to the development of our country, as well as strengthen cooperation with foreign countries whose languages they are learning.

As a result of learning foreign languages, our communicative abilities improve, it becomes possible to watch films and read books in their original languages. Along with that, by learning foreign languages, our knowledge of our mother tongue improves, concentration improves, mathematical abilities increase, the ability to perceive information makes up progress, and learning a foreign language also involves interacting with people. A person who knows multiple languages can easily engage in easy communication with the people around them.

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